

Effects of Digitally Recorded Patient Education Before Esophageal Manometry Procedure

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Background

- Esophageal dysmotility occurs when the esophagus fails to function properly
- Achalasia occurs in 1-3 cases per 100,000 people
- High-resolution esophageal manometry (HREM) measures motility in patients with suspected esophageal disorders
- HREM = the gold standard in diagnosing esophageal motility disorders

Problem

- HREM is performed in GI (gastro-intestinal) motility clinics
- Variety of referral sources to GI clinic received; unknown patient baseline knowledge of HREM
- Current educational tool is a 1-page form that lacks procedural information
- Patient anxiety is a commonly observed phenomenon
- Average patient satisfaction survey score is 89%
- 8% of procedures are aborted due to an elevated anxiety level

Purpose

- To develop a digital recording about the HREM procedure to enhance the existing patient educational tool
- The purpose of the recording is to:
 - ❖ Improve knowledge
 - ❖ Reduce procedural anxiety
 - ❖ Increase patient satisfaction > 95%
 - ❖ Reduce the percentage of patients aborting the HREM procedure secondary to anxiety to < 2

Supporting Framework: Self-Regulation Theory

Model of Information Processing in Self-Regulation Theory. Adaptation from Johnson, J. E., Fieler, V. K., Jones, L. S., Wlasowicz, G. S., & Mitchell, M. L. (1997). *Self-Regulation theory: Applying theory to your practicencology* Nursing Press.

Methods

<p>STUDY DESIGN</p> <p>Pre-Post Test</p> <p>Standard care group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 1-page educational form + RN & MD verbal preparation <p>Implementation Group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Standard care + review of an 8-minute educational video before manometry 	<p>SAMPLE & SETTING</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purposive, convenience sampling • 24 participants • Setting: ambulatory GI Motility clinic within a health center in Southern California • Inclusion: all adults > 18 years of age, English language skills • Exclusion: <18 years of age, inability to understand English 	<p>PROCEDURE</p> <p>Standard care group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Pre and post-test on knowledge and anxiety <p>Implementation Group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Pre and post-test on knowledge and anxiety ❖ + post-test satisfaction
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Results

A significant increase in knowledge occurred in the control and implementation groups following HREM digital education

Results

- Anxiety**
- A meaningful reduction of anxiety scores in both the control (mean reduction from 7.1 to 5.5 out of 12) and implementation group (mean reduction from 8.25 to 7.16 out of 12)
- Satisfaction**
- 100% of patients liked the recorded education & recommended others to watch the recording before esophageal manometry procedure
- Procedural Abortion Rate**
- No cases were aborted during the implementation phase

Discussion

- Findings support the positive impact of recorded patient education as evidenced in the literature
- Potential of a Hawthorne effect needs to be considered
- Digitally recorded education offers the benefit of a standardized method of teaching
- Reduced aborted procedures can result in cost savings and also improve patient satisfaction

Conclusion

- Additional studies with a larger sample size is needed
- Lessons learned from this project can be used to guide patient satisfaction improvements in other types of ambulatory care clinics